

Rifampicin and its derivatives: stability, disposition, and affinity towards pregnane X receptor employing 2D and 3D primary human hepatocytes

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Rifampicin
Hepatocyte spheroid
Cytochrome P450
Pregnane X receptor
Metabolism
Molecular docking

ABSTRACT

Rifampicin is a model ligand of the pregnane X receptor (PXR), the nuclear receptor involved in the regulation of cytochrome P450 3A4 (CYP3A4). Rifampicin forms several degradation products and metabolites of which 25-desacetyl rifampicin is the most abundant *in vivo*. Here, we aimed to study both the stability and metabolism of rifampicin in media and 2D and 3D primary human hepatocytes (PHHs). Additionally, we analyzed interactions of rifampicin derivatives with PXR. We described that rifampicin gradually degrades by more than 50 % in the medium partly into quinone over 72 h. We observed 25-desacetyl rifampicin in 2D PHHs but not in 3D PHHs. Contrary, rifampicin was converted into quinone in a one-direction process in media of 3D PHHs. The potency of rifampicin and its derivatives to activate human PXR was arranged as follows: 3-formylrifampicin SV > rifampicin quinone > rifampicin > rifampicin N-oxide > 25-desacetyl rifampicin, respectively, but none activates mouse and rat PXR. The binding differences between rifampicin and 25-desacetyl rifampicin were modeled *in silico*. Finally, we showed that overexpressed uptake organic anion transporting polypeptide 1B1 (OATP1B1) potentiated activation of PXR by rifampicin and rifampicin quinone, but overexpressed efflux multidrug resistance protein 1 (MDR1) decreased PXR activation by all derivatives.

1. Introduction

The pregnane X receptor (PXR) is a ligand-regulated transcription factor mainly expressed in the liver and the intestine. So far, numerous target genes of PXR have been identified including cytochrome P450 3A4 (CYP3A4), which is one of the most important drug-metabolizing enzymes [1,2].

Among structurally diverse PXR activators, antibiotic rifampicin represents one of the most clear-cut ligands of human PXR and is frequently utilized in studies focusing on PXR function [3]. Rifampicin is predominantly eliminated through biliary excretion in the form of desacetyl metabolite [4]. It was reported that human arylacetamide deacetylase (AADAC), a serine esterase expressed in the liver, catalyzes

the deacetylation of rifampicin. It is worthy of note, that 25-desacetyl rifampicin showed a lesser potency to transactivate CYP3A4 promoter in gene reporter studies when compared to a parent drug [5]. Besides, rifampicin can be hydrolyzed to 3-formylrifampicin SV [6]. This metabolite could be found in human serum and urine after rifampicin treatment [7,8]. It can be also present as an impurity in rifampicin products along with rifampicin N-oxide and rifampicin quinone [9]. Specifically, the latter is the product of nonenzymatic autooxidation of unstable rifampicin [10]. An occurrence of rifampicin quinone was also detected in human urine [8], however, its systemic exposure was very low following oral administration of rifampicin in rats. This is consistent with findings, that rifampicin quinone itself is considerably reduced to rifampicin *in vivo* [11].

Abbreviations: AADAC, arylacetamide deacetylase; ABCB1, ATP binding cassette subfamily B member 1; ANOVA, one-way analysis of variance; CYP3A4, cytochrome P450 3A4; DMSO, dimethyl sulfoxide; ECACC, European Collection of Cell Cultures; MDR1, multidrug resistance protein 1; mPXR, mouse PXR; OATP1B1, organic anion transporting polypeptide 1B1; PCN, pregnenolone 16 α -carbonitrile; PHH, primary human hepatocyte; PXR, pregnane X receptor; QC, quality control; RID, receptor interaction domain; rPXR, rat PXR; UAS, upstream activator sequence; ULA, ultra-low attachment.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcp.2024.116500>

Received 12 May 2024; Received in revised form 16 August 2024; Accepted 19 August 2024

Available online 22 August 2024

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Rifampicin entry through the basolateral hepatocyte membrane is one of the determinants influencing rifampicin-induced PXR activation. In more detail, the hepatic uptake of rifampicin was shown to be carrier-mediated by liver-specific transporters such as organic anion transporting polypeptide-C (OATP-C, OATP1B1) and OATP8 (OATP1B3) [12–14]. It has been further documented that OATP-C expression leads to increased intracellular rifampicin accumulation with a subsequent potentiation of PXR activation [13].

Additionally, rifampicin is a substrate of efflux pump ATP binding cassette subfamily B member 1 (ABCB1, also known as P-glycoprotein or multidrug resistance protein 1, MDR1). Moreover, the amount of MDR1 was associated with changes in the extent to which rifampicin could induce CYP3A4 expression [15]. In general, the hepatocyte canalicular membrane localized MDR1 transporter is responsible for the excretion of endogenous and exogenous substrates to bile in the liver [16].

Of note, rifampicin induces its own elimination, which is practically completed within a week of repeated rifampicin administration resulting in a reduction of rifampicin half-life. This is believed to be due to an increase in hepatic deacetylation and enhancement of biliary excretion [4,17].

Although the pharmacokinetic properties of rifampicin itself have been studied, there is much less known about the molecular aspects of rifampicin disposition in human hepatocytes and the action of rifampicin derivatives such as rifampicin metabolites and degradation products on PXR in regulation of xenobiotic metabolism. Additionally, rifampicin metabolic stability and profiling have not been done and compared in 2D and 3D primary human hepatocytes (PHHs).

In the present study, we for the first time tracked and compared the fate of rifampicin and its derivatives in both culture medium and intracellular space in *in vitro* models of 2D and 3D PHHs. Moreover, rifampicin derivatives were described regarding their potency to activate PXR or its orthologs in gene reporter studies and by *in silico* docking analysis. Additionally, it has been previously reported that rifampicin disposition is controlled by uptake and efflux transporters, but current literature is scarce on the transport of rifampicin derivatives through hepatocyte cell membranes. Therefore, we set out to evaluate whether OATP1B1- and MDR1-facilitated transport plays any role in the hepatic disposition of rifampicin derivatives and PXR-induced CYP3A4 expression. Finally, the effect of rifampicin on AADAC, OATP1B1, OATP1B3, and MDR1 expression, genes involved in metabolism and transport, was investigated in long-term experiments employing 3D PHHs to help explain the processes responsible for autoinduction of rifampicin elimination in the liver.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

Rifampicin, 3-formylrifamycin SV, rifampicin quinone, rifampicin N-oxide, pregnenolone 16 α -carbonitrile (PCN), and DMSO were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (nowadays Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). 25-desacetyl-rifampicin was gained from Toronto Research Chemicals (TRC, Toronto, Canada). Ammonium acetate GR was obtained from Lach-Ner (Neratovice, the Czech Republic). All other solvents and reagents were of an analytical grade and purchased from established suppliers such as Merck (Darmstadt, Germany) and VWR International (Stribrna Skalice, the Czech Republic). Milli-Q water was produced by a Millipore water purification system (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany).

All stock solutions were prepared in DMSO (1,000 \times) and stored at -70 C.

2.2. Primary human hepatocyte (PHH) spheroids

Cryopreserved human hepatocytes from three donors were acquired from BioIVT (Westbury, New York, USA). Donor characteristics were as follows: donor 1 – female, 27 years, African American, donor 2 –

female, 30 years, Hispanic, donor 3 – female, 39 years, Caucasian. 3D spheroids were prepared by spontaneous self-aggregation of PHHs based on the previously reported protocol [18,19].

Briefly, cells were seeded onto ultra-low attachment (ULA) 96-well plates (Corning, New York, USA) at a density of 1,500 cells per well, centrifuged (at 130 \times g/2 min) and cultivated in disclosed PHH medium, William's E medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) enriched with insulin (10 μ g/ml)–transferrin (5.5 μ g/ml)–sodium selenite (6.7 ng/ml) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA), L-glutamine (2 mM)–penicillin (100 U/ml)–streptomycin (100 μ g/ml), 100 nM dexamethasone (Sigma-Aldrich, nowadays Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), and 10 % fetal bovine serum (HyClone, Logan, Utah, USA).

After 6 days, half of the medium was exchanged for serum-free PHH medium. On day 8 post-seeding, PHH spheroids were treated in serum-free PHH medium with rifampicin, 25-desacetyl-rifampicin, 3-formylrifamycin SV, rifampicin quinone, and rifampicin N-oxide (10 μ M) at indicated time points ranging from 4 to 168 h. Conditioned PHH medium was changed regularly every 2–3 days within treatment interval.

2.3. 2D PHH monolayer cultures

Cryopreserved PHHs (donors 1–3) were seeded in PHH medium enriched with 10 % fetal bovine serum at a density of 350,000 cells per well of rat tail collagen type I-coated 24-well plates (catalog number 354408, Corning, New York, USA). Cultivation medium was exchanged for serum-free PHH medium 2 h later when PHHs were attached to the plate surface. The next day, 2D PHHs were treated with rifampicin (10 μ M) in serum-free PHH medium for 24 h or 48 h.

2.4. Stability testing of rifampicin and rifampicin quinone by HPLC

Rifampicin and rifampicin quinone were diluted at 10 μ M in a serum-free PHH medium to determine their stability over 72 h at 37 $^{\circ}$ C (analyzed time points included 0, 4, 24, 48, and 72 h). The collected samples were stored at -70 C. Later, the samples were thawed, filtered (Millex PVDF syringe filter with a 0.22 μ m pore size, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), and analyzed by HPLC.

Briefly, a concentration of compounds was simultaneously determined by the developed LC-UV method performed on Prominence Liquid Chromatograph UFLC XR (LC-20 series) with UV/VIS detector SPD-20A (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan). The chromatographic column Avantor ACE Excel C18-AR (100 \times 3 mm; particle size 3 μ m, VWR International) with precolumn Guard (C18 cartridge, 4 \times 2 mm ID; Phenomenex, Torrance, USA) was selected for the separation. The mobile phase A was ammonium acetate (30 mM, pH=6.3) and phase B was methanol. The following gradient was applied: 0.0–9.0 min (65 \rightarrow 90 % B), 9.0–11.0 min (90 % B), 11.0–11.1 min (90 \rightarrow 65 % B), and 11.1–15.1 min (65 % B). The flow rate was set to 0.4 ml/min and the column was maintained at 25 C. A sample volume of 10 μ l was injected. The data were collected at 330 nm. Data acquisition and quantification were performed using the LabSolutions software (version 5.97 SP 1, Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan). The chromatogram showed the separation of all tested compounds.

The calibration curves were created from nine calibration levels 0.3, 0.5, 1, 2, 5, 8, 10, 12, and 15 μ M or rifampicin in serum-free PHH medium. The quality control (QC) samples reached concentrations of 0.3, 1, 5, and 12 μ M. The calibration curves were created using a least-square linear regression fit with $1/x^2$ weighting in GraphPad Prism (version 9.3.1., California, USA). Further, the determination of linearity, accuracy, and precision followed the guidance for Bioanalytical Method Validation, 2018 by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (available online at: www.fda.gov).

The data were acquired from at least three independent measurements done with freshly prepared samples.

2.5. Concentration analyses of rifampicin and its products in PHHs

3D PHHs were treated with rifampicin or rifampicin quinone (10 μ M) for 24 or 72 h. Then, equal volumes of either conditioned cell free-media or conditioned media enriched with spheroids (in a ratio of 80 μ l per spheroid) were collected. In the case of experiments with 2D PHHs, cells were exposed to rifampicin (10 μ M) for 48 h. After, conditioned PHH media were collected with cells harvested by scraping. All media samples were kept frozen until further use.

Later, samples were thawed and mixed with acetonitrile in a ratio 1:3 (v/v). Samples enriched with spheroids or harvested cells were further homogenized by glass beads and spun down to obtain supernatant. A concentration of compounds in both conditioned cell-free media and conditioned media enriched with lysed spheroids or harvested cells was determined by HPLC in the same manner as described in a Stability testing section.

The data were presented as the mean \pm SD of three independent measurements employing 3 different PHH donors.

2.6. RT-qPCR

Total RNA was isolated from 30 spheroids or 350,000 cells in the case of 2D PHHs per each condition using the phenol–chloroform extraction. The RNA concentration was quantified on a Nanodrop 1000 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). Reverse transcription of RNA to cDNA was performed using a High-capacity cDNA reverse transcription kit (catalog number 4374966, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). Subsequent qPCR reactions were carried out on the QuantStudio 6 Flex Real-Time PCR System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) with TaqMan Universal master mix II (catalog number 4440047, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) and TaqMan assays (FAM) such as CYP3A4 (Hs00604506_m1), CYP2B6 (Hs04183483_g1), CYP2C9 (Hs04260376_m1), AADAC (Hs00153677_m1), OATPB1 (Hs00272374_m1), OATPB3 (Hs00251986_m1), ABCB1 (MDR1, Hs00184500_m1), and TBP (Hs00427620_m1) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). The program was set as follows: a first step at 95 °C for 10 min to activate polymerase and 40 cycles of denaturation at 95 °C for 15 s and annealing/elongation at 60 °C for 60 s.

The Ct values of target genes were normalized to the Ct values of reference gene TBP and showed as the fold change expression to corresponding DMSO control at the indicated time point (set as 1). All 3D PHH results are presented as the mean \pm SD acquired from at least three independent biological measurements run in technical duplicates.

2.7. Plasmids

The p3A4-luc reporter construct (100 or 150 ng/well) was previously described elsewhere [20]. It harbors the basal promoter (−361/+53) with the proximal PXR response element (ER6) as well as the distal xenobiotic responsive enhancer module XREM (−7835/−7208) of the CYP3A4 gene. Both sequences were inserted into the pGL4.10 basic luciferase reporter vector (Promega, Madison, Wisconsin, USA). The expression plasmid for PXR transcript variant 1 (pSG5-hPXR, 100 ng/well, NM_003889.3) was described in our previous work [21]. pRL-TK (30 ng/well) is the control vector constitutively expressing Renilla luciferase (Promega, Madison, Wisconsin, USA).

The Rhesus monkey PXR expression vector (100 ng/well, OMB04674, NM_001032882.3) as well as mPXR (100 ng/well, OMu17834, NM_010936.3) and rPXR (100 ng/well, ORa13120, NM_052980.2) expression vectors encoding mouse (*Mus musculus*) and rat (*Rattus norvegicus*) PXR, respectively, were purchased from Genscript (Piscataway, New Jersey, USA). hPXR var. 2 (100 ng/well, OHu23284, NM_022002.2) is a plasmid expressing transcript variant 2 of human PXR, which is translated into a protein containing additional 39 amino

acids at the N-terminus compared to PXR var. 1 (Genscript, Piscataway, New Jersey, USA).

Expression vectors for human OATP1B1 transporter (200 ng/well, SC116071, NM_006446) and human MDR1 transporter (200 ng/well, OHu102681, NM_001348945.1) were acquired from OriGene (Rockville, Maryland, USA) and Genscript (Piscataway, New Jersey, USA), respectively. Expression (empty) plasmid pcDNA3 (200 ng/well) was obtained from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, Massachusetts, USA).

Plasmids for two-hybrid assay: pGL4-UAS 9x (120 ng/well) is the construct containing 9 repeats of upstream activator sequence (UAS), which drives transcription of a luciferase reporter gene as a response to the binding of a fusion protein bearing GAL4 DNA-binding domain (pGL4.35, Promega, Madison, Wisconsin, USA). G-PXR-W (100 ng/well) is an expression plasmid encoding the GAL4 DNA-binding domain fused to the ligand-binding domain of human wild-type PXR [22]. pVP16-SRC-1-RID (100 ng/well) is an expression plasmid, which gives rise to the receptor interaction domain (RID) of PXR coactivator SRC-1 fused to VP16 activation domain of herpes simplex virus [22]. In principle, a ligand binding to PXR fused protein results in the interaction with SRC-1-RID and is detectable through activation of the pGL4-UAS 9x reporter construct.

2.8. Gene reporter and two-hybrid assays

Liver cancer HepG2 cells were purchased from the European Collection of Cell Cultures (ECACC, UK). The passage number was never higher than 25. The cells were seeded onto 48-well plates (catalog number 150687, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) at a density of 110,000 cells/well and maintained at 37 °C in a humidified 5 % CO₂ atmosphere. Cells were cultivated in DMEM medium (Sigma-Aldrich, nowadays Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine serum. The next day after seeding, HepG2 cells were transfected with vectors using a lipid-based Lipofectamine 3000 transfection reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) according to the manufacturer's recommendations for 24 or 48 h.

Then, the conditioned medium was aspirated and replaced with Opti-MEM medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) containing 5 % fetal bovine serum as well as tested compounds such as rifampicin or its derivatives at indicated concentrations. The firefly and Renilla luciferase activities were analyzed in cell lysates after treatment employing the Dual-Luciferase Reporter Assay System (Promega, Madison, Wisconsin, USA). Data are displayed as the fold change in Renilla luciferase-normalized firefly luciferase activities to corresponding DMSO control (set as 1).

The results are presented as the mean \pm SD. Three independent biological measurements were run in technical triplicates.

2.9. ATP assay

ATP content in PHH spheroids was assessed by CellTiter-Glo Luminescent Cell Viability Assay (catalog number G7571, Promega, Madison, Wisconsin, USA) following the previously reported protocol [19]. In short, each single spheroid was exposed to the reagent for 20 min at 37 °C. The generated luminescent signal, which is proportional to the amount of ATP, was measured by the plate reader Synergy2 (BioTek, Winooski, Vermont, USA). The luminescence output is presented as a relative change to DMSO control (set as 100 %).

All data are shown as the mean \pm SD obtained from three independent biological measurements run in technical triplicates.

2.10. Molecular docking studies

The PXR crystal structures were downloaded from the RCSB Protein Data Bank (<https://www.rcsb.org>) (PDB ID: 1SKX and 8E3N) [23,24]. The PXR binding domains were checked for possible errors and clashes

and further prepared by a standard procedure using AutoDock Tools 1.5.7 [25]. Specifically, water molecules were removed, polar hydrogens were added, and Kollman charges were assigned.

The structures of 25-desacetyl rifampicin and rifampicin were drawn in PerkinElmer Chem3D (version 20.0.0.41, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) and retrieved from PDB (ID: 1SKX), respectively, and underwent energy minimization using the inbuilt MM2 force field. The structures were exported as PDB files and then processed by AutoDock Tools. The adjustments included a calculation of Gasteiger charges. Non-polar hydrogens were merged, and the torsion tree was formed.

The target grid box defining the PXR active site was defined by a box with side lengths of $30 \times 30 \times 30$ grid points (1 Å spacing) and centered at 1SKX (11, 77, -1) [24].

Molecular docking studies with rifampicin and 25-desacetyl rifampicin were carried out by AutoDock Vina 1.1.2 [26]. Shortly, exhaustiveness was set at 16, five binding modes were allowed, and the default setting was maintained for other parameters. Each ligand had three separate runs with random seeds, and the final docking score is the average docking score of matching poses. Docking outcomes were visualized by the PyMOL system (version 2.5, Schrödinger). The 2D diagrams of ligand–protein interactions were created using a graphical system LigPlot+ (version 2.2.8) [27].

2.11. Statistical analyses

All statistical analyses were performed in GraphPad Prism (version 9.3.1., California, USA).

The concentration–response curve was fitted by nonlinear regression analyses on log-transformed concentration values and EC_{50} values were determined. E_{max} was constrained to the detected maximal fold induction to prevent extrapolation of the curve fit beyond the range of acquired results.

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Dunnett's post hoc test was used to compare expression changes or viability between DMSO- and tested compound-treated PHH spheroids or HepG2 cells.

The differences in tested compound-induced p3A4-luc reporter construct activities between HepG2 cells transfected with pOATP1B1 or

pMDR1 and those transfected with empty pcDNA3 plasmid were analyzed by an unpaired *t*-test. *p* values < 0.05 were considered significant.

3. Results

3.1. Stability of rifampicin in PHH medium

Rifampicin is labile and its hydroquinone moiety undergoes autoxidation to form rifampicin quinone at physiological pH [10]. Indeed, we could detect a gradual decrease in the concentration of rifampicin in PHH medium at 37 °C within a time-course of 3 days. A decrease was only partially compensated by an increase in the concentration of its oxidized counterpart proposing a more complex degradation pathway of rifampicin in PHH medium (Fig. 1A). In parallel, rifampicin quinone itself revealed dramatic instability in PHH medium, which could not be ascribed to its spontaneous reduction to rifampicin (Fig. 1B).

3.2. Activation of PXR by rifampicin derivatives

Due to the instability of rifampicin and the presence of related compounds in rifampicin preparations [9], we set out to compare the affinity of rifampicin, rifampicin quinone, rifampicin N-oxide, 25-desacetyl rifampicin, and 3-formylrifamycin SV towards PXR employing gene reporter assays.

Firstly, hepatic HepG2 cells transfected with the expression vector for PXR and CYP3A4 reporter construct (p3A4-luc) were treated with tested compounds at indicated concentrations for 24 h (Fig. 2A). EC_{50} values were calculated based on concentration–response curves. The main rifampicin metabolite 25-desacetyl rifampicin showed the lowest PXR affinity among tested compounds ($EC_{50} = 86.57 \mu\text{M}$). The potency to activate PXR by remaining compounds could be arranged in the following order: 3-formylrifamycin SV ($EC_{50} = 0.87 \mu\text{M}$) > rifampicin quinone ($EC_{50} = 1.14 \mu\text{M}$) > rifampicin ($EC_{50} = 1.46 \mu\text{M}$) > rifampicin N-oxide ($EC_{50} = 2.71 \mu\text{M}$), respectively.

Next, the two-hybrid assay was performed to identify whether rifampicin derivatives are indeed direct PXR ligands. In the experiments,

Fig. 1. Rifampicin (A) and rifampicin quinone (B) stability detected by HPLC in the serum-free PHH medium within 72 h at 37 °C. Results are presented as stacked bar charts. Bars depict time-dependent depletion in the total amount of rifampicin and rifampicin quinone relative to that at time 0 h (set as 100 %). Subcategories of the bar show percentages of both compounds individually with the numbers indicated within corresponding fractions. Some bars are not reaching 100 % due to further degradation of rifampicin and rifampicin quinone.

Gene reporter assays

Fig. 2. A comparison of rifampicin and its derivatives to activate PXR in gene reporter assays. (A) HepG2 cells were transfected with p3A4-luc reporter construct, pSG5-hPXR, and pRL-TK for 24 h and then treated with compounds at indicated concentrations for another 24 h. EC_{50} , half maximal effective concentrations are displayed for each tested compound. The chemical structures of rifampicin and its derivatives are depicted. (B) HepG2 cells were transfected with pGL4-UAS 9x, G-PXR-W, pVP16-SRC1-RID, and pRL-TK for 24 h and then treated with compounds at 10 μ M for another 24 h. (C) HepG2 cells were transfected with a p3A4-luc reporter construct and pRL-TK along with hPXR var. 2, monkey PXR, mouse PXR (mPXR), or rat PXR (rPXR) for 24 h and then treated with rifampicin and its derivatives at 10 μ M or PCN at 50 μ M for another 24 h. (A-C) Data are presented as the fold change in Renilla luciferase-normalized firefly luciferase activities to DMSO control (set as 1). (B-C) ANOVA with Dunnett's post hoc test was used to compare tested compound-induced changes in gene reporter activity relative to DMSO control. * indicates $p < 0.05$, ** indicates $p < 0.01$, and *** indicates $p < 0.001$.

HepG2 cells were exposed to tested compounds at 10 μ M for 24 h. All interrogated rifampicin derivatives manifested a comparable binding to PXR leading to about 3-fold activation of gene reporter construct, whereas 25-desacetylriofampicin showed only 1.8-fold induction (Fig. 2B).

Rifampicin is a prototype activator of human but not rodent PXR [28]. To our knowledge, rifampicin derivatives have not been previously tested regarding their affinity towards PXR orthologs. For that reason, we employed gene reporter assays using HepG2 cells transfected with CYP3A4 reporter construct (p3A4-luc) along with expression vectors for different PXR orthologs such as monkey, mouse, or rat. The activity of the CYP3A4 reporter vector was strongly induced by rifampicin and its derivatives (at 10 μ M) in experiments with concomitantly transfected hPXR var. 2 expression vector, which was used as a reference of human PXR. The exception was 25-desacetylriofampicin, which practically did not affect a signal generated by the CYP3A4 reporter vector. This was also true for PCN (at 50 μ M). Next, we could observe an analogical induction pattern delivered by rifampicin derivatives for monkey PXR, but relative CYP3A4 induction was much lower than that mediated by human PXR (hPXR var. 2). In sharp contrast, rifampicin derivatives could not activate mouse and rat PXR in gene reporter studies. As expected, PCN, a model activator of rodent PXR [28], significantly stimulated the transactivation of CYP3A4 by mouse and rat PXR (Fig. 2C).

3.3. *In silico* study on the interaction of rifampicin and 25-desacetylriofampicin with PXR

To elucidate the interactions between rifampicin or 25-desacetylriofampicin and the PXR binding site, we performed *in silico* simulations with two different PXR structures (PDB ID: 1SKX and 8E3N) [23,24].

In concordance with [24], rifampicin formed hydrogen bond interactions with Q285 and H407 as well as several hydrophobic interactions at the PXR ligand-binding site (PDB ID: 1SKX) (Figs. 3 and 4A). Its docking score was low (-11.5 kcal/mol), likely due to used favorable static template acquired from rifampicin bound PXR crystal structure (PDB ID: 1SKX) [24]. Although 25-desacetylriofampicin also created several hydrophobic interactions, it did not form any hydrogen bonds (Figs. 3 and 4A). Its docking score was -7.6 kcal/mol suggesting a weaker binding interaction.

Interestingly, we found out that rifampicin and 25-

desacetylriofampicin bind to the same PXR binding site (PDB ID: 1SKX), but with different orientations (Fig. 4B). To gain insight into structural changes of PXR protein, we overlaid PXR ligand-binding domains with helix 2 (H2) (PDB ID: 8E3N) and without H2 (PDB ID: 1SKX). The latter was docked with 25-desacetylriofampicin and rifampicin. It was found that 25-desacetylriofampicin could have a clash with the H2 position different from that of rifampicin (Fig. 4B). In addition to missing hydrogen bond interactions, the unfavorable clash [23] could help to explain a lower PXR affinity of 25-desacetylriofampicin.

Analogically to [29], the *in silico* model allows us to speculate that rifampicin and its metabolite may enter the ligand-binding domain via the H2 region by a flickering gate mechanism. Therefore, the H2 region might act as a dynamic gate that opens and closes in response to ligand binding.

3.4. Induction of CYP3A4, CYP2B6, and CYP2C9 mRNA expression by rifampicin derivatives in 3D PHH system

3D PHH spheroids have emerged as a potential new gold standard of *in vitro* liver cell models maintaining a relevant hepatic phenotype for several weeks in the culture [30]. Taking advantage of stable hepatic functionality in 3D PHHs, we exposed the cells to 25-desacetylriofampicin (10 μ M) within a period of 5 days. The treatment resulted in a maximal induction of CYP3A4, CYP2B6, and CYP2C9 mRNA consistently on day 2 being 2.6, 2, and 1.6-fold, respectively. After reaching peak response, CYP3A4 mRNA expression slightly declined on day 3 revealing a bell-shaped time-induction pattern but that trend was not seen for CYP2B6 and CYP2C9 mRNA (Fig. 5A).

A comparison of treatment among other rifampicin derivatives demonstrated similar fold changes in CYP3A4, CYP2B6, and CYP2C9 mRNA levels on day 3. The only exception was rifampicin N-oxide, as by which CYP2B6 mRNA expression was increased but the changes were somewhat variable among donors to reach statistical significance (Fig. 5B).

3.5. Cell viability of 3D PHHs after treatment with rifampicin and its derivatives

3D PHHs were exposed to rifampicin and its derivatives for 72 h and analyzed regarding their viability, which was expressed as a change in

Fig. 3. 2D diagrams of interactions between rifampicin or 25-desacetylriofampicin and a ligand-binding site of PXR. The 2D diagrams generated by the LigPlot+ portray the molecular interactions between rifampicin (left) and 25-desacetylriofampicin (right) with the residues of PXR that form the ligand-binding site (PDB ID: 1SKX). The hydrogen bonds are represented by green dashed lines and red arcs depict hydrophobic interactions labeled by the position of PXR residues. The red circles indicate equivalent PXR residues for both compounds. The position of the acetyl group at C25 (highlighted in green) is shown in the blue circle.

Fig. 4. 3D interactions of rifampicin and 25-desacetyl rifampicin with PXR at the ligand-binding site. (A) The outcome of molecular docking shows interactions between rifampicin (left, green) or 25-desacetyl rifampicin (right, yellow) and the residues of PXR that form the ligand-binding site (PDB ID: 1SKX). The hydrogen bonds are represented by yellow dashed lines. The Q285 residue that interacts with the acetyl group of rifampicin is colored light blue, while 25-desacetyl rifampicin does not have this interaction. The positions of residues are indicated in boxes. (B) The left image shows superimposed 1SKX (together with bound rifampicin (the dark orange, 4-methyl-1-piperazinyl ring was not observed), docked rifampicin (green) and 25-desacetyl rifampicin (yellow)) and 8E3N PXR crystal structures. The H2 position is indicated in a light blue color (present only in 8E3N) and dark blue as modeled could be a gate mechanism to allow enter the small molecules to the PXR ligand-binding pocket. The right image depicts a close-up view of interactions between docked rifampicin (green) or 25-desacetyl rifampicin (yellow) or bound rifampicin (dark orange) with a ligand-binding domain of PXR. 25-desacetyl rifampicin has a steric clash with the H2 region, which is not identical to that of rifampicin.

ATP content. 3-formylrifamycin SV induced slight cytotoxicity but other tested compounds seem to be non-toxic at 10 μ M concentration (Fig. 5C).

3.6. Metabolism of rifampicin in 2D and 3D PHH cultures

In the next series of experiments, we studied the metabolic turnover of rifampicin in PHHs in both 2D and 3D settings. Rifampicin was intensively metabolized by 2D PHHs generating 25-desacetyl rifampicin on day 2 (Table 1). Importantly, we could not detect rifampicin quinone in the 2D PHH monolayer.

In stark contrast, rifampicin-treated 3D PHHs could not produce 25-

desacetyl rifampicin, but time-dependent changes in a concentration of rifampicin were found to be attributed to its oxidation to rifampicin quinone. Moreover, rifampicin is retained in spheroids as deduced from its higher concentration in a conditioned medium enriched with lysed spheroids than in a corresponding conditioned cell-free medium. No accumulation of rifampicin quinone was detected inside the cells as both corresponding conditioned medium and conditioned medium enriched with lysed spheroids provided comparable concentrations of rifampicin quinone at 24 h and 72 h (Table 1).

When 3D PHHs were treated with rifampicin quinone only, again no accumulation of rifampicin quinone was seen inside the cells. The formation of rifampicin from rifampicin quinone can likely be held

Fig. 5. CYP3A4, CYP2B6, and CYP2C9 mRNA expression changes and cell viability in 3D PHHs following treatment with rifampicin and its derivatives. 3D PHH spheroids (donors 1–3) were exposed to rifampicin or its derivatives (10 μM) for an indicated time ranging from 12 to 120 h. CYP3A4, CYP2B6, and CYP2C9 mRNA expression levels were analyzed by RT-qPCR. The data are shown as the fold change expression relative to the corresponding DMSO control at the same time (set as 1). ANOVA with Dunnett's post hoc test was used to either compare time-dependent 25-desacetyl rifampicin-induced changes in CYP3A4, CYP2B6, and CYP2C9 mRNA expression relative to time 0 (set as 1) (A) or tested compound-induced changes in CYP3A4, CYP2B6, and CYP2C9 mRNA expression 72 h post-treatment relative to DMSO control (B). * indicates $p < 0.05$, ** indicates $p < 0.01$, and *** indicates $p < 0.001$. (C) 3D PHHs were treated with rifampicin and its derivatives for 72 h at a concentration of 10 μM . Then, ATP content was quantified and shown as a relative change to DMSO control (set as 100 %). ANOVA with Dunnett's post hoc test was used to compare tested compound-induced changes in cell viability relative to DMSO control. * indicates $p < 0.05$.

Table 1

Changes in the concentration of rifampicin or rifampicin quinone after its exposure to 2D and 3D PHHs.

2D PHHs						
treatment by rifampicin (10 μM)						
time of treatment (h)	rifampicin	medium with lysed 2D PHHs	rifampicin quinone	medium with lysed 2D PHHs	25-desacetyl rifampicin	medium with lysed 2D PHHs
48	7.1 (± 0.9)		ND		4.6 (± 2.0)	
3D PHHs						
treatment by rifampicin (10 μM)						
time of treatment (h)	rifampicin	medium	medium with lysed 3D PHHs	rifampicin quinone	medium	medium with lysed 3D PHHs
24	7.9 (± 0.4)		9.1 (± 1.7)	3.4 (± 1.2)	3.6 (± 0.9)	ND
72	7.0 (± 0.6)		8.7 (± 0.7)	2.0 (± 1.0)	2.1 (± 0.9)	ND
treatment by rifampicin quinone (10 μM)						
time of treatment (h)	rifampicin	medium	medium with lysed 3D PHHs	rifampicin quinone	medium	medium with lysed 3D PHHs
24	0.4 (± 0.0)*		1.3 (± 0.4)	10.6 (± 1.1)	10.9 (± 0.7)	ND
72	0.4**		1.0 (± 0.1)	8.6 (± 0.6)	9.0 (± 0.1)	ND

3-formylrifamycin SV and rifampicin N-oxide were below the minimal detection limit in both settings concentrations (μM) are presented as mean (\pm SD)

* detected in 2 donors out of 3

** detected in 1 donor out of 3

ND, not detected

responsible for the observed changes in 3D PHHs as suggested by a higher rifampicin concentration in conditioned medium enriched with lysed spheroids than in corresponding cell-free medium (Table 1).

3.7. A transport of rifampicin derivatives by OATP1B1 transporter

Hepatic OATP1B1 is a known uptake transporter for rifampicin [12–14]. To uncover the role of OATP1B1 transporter in the disposition of rifampicin derivatives, we performed a gene reporter assay with HepG2 cells transfected with expression vectors for OATP1B1 and PXR along with CYP3A4 reporter construct (p3A4-luc). HepG2 cells were employed as the basal level of OATP1B1 expression has been reported to be lower than that of another available hepatic cell line Huh-7 [31]. Since the intracellular concentration of PXR ligands is the driving force of PXR action, we assumed that OATP1B1-enhanced uptake of rifampicin derivatives could potentiate PXR-mediated transactivation of CYP3A4. Thereby, we indirectly identified rifampicin and rifampicin quinone as OATP1B1 substrates as both compounds could more increase CYP3A4 reporter activity in HepG2 cells transfected with OATP1B1 when compared to those transfected with empty vector. The effect of both compounds was a concentration-dependent and a difference was

significant at 1 μ M concentration. A similar trend could be ascertained for other tested rifampicin derivatives, but it did not reach statistical significance (Fig. 6).

3.8. A transport of rifampicin derivatives by MDR1 transporter

Rifampicin is a recognized substrate of MDR1 transporter [15]. Important though, it is not known whether rifampicin derivatives could be also carried by MDR1. To this end, we transfected HepG2 cells with expression vectors for MDR1 and PXR along with CYP3A4 reporter construct (p3A4-luc). Again, HepG2 cells were used as the basal level of MDR1 expression is much lower compared to that of another available liver cell line Huh-7 [31]. The experimental design assumed that MDR1-driven efflux of rifampicin derivative could reduce its intracellular concentration resulting in weaker PXR-mediated transactivation of CYP3A4. As shown in Fig. 7, all tested compounds were indirectly demonstrated as MDR1 substrates as they could less stimulate CYP3A4 reporter activity in HepG2 cells transfected with MDR1 than in their counterparts deficient in this transporter despite identical tested compound concentrations. The effect of MDR1 overexpression was generally not significantly pronounced at the highest tested concentrations except

Gene reporter assay 12 h-treatment HepG2 cells

Fig. 6. The effect of forced OATP1B1 expression on induction of CYP3A4 gene reporter by rifampicin and its derivatives. HepG2 cells were transfected with p3A4-luc reporter construct, pSG5-hPXR, and pRL-TK along with pOATP1B1 or pcDNA3 for 24 h and then treated with rifampicin and its derivatives at indicated concentrations for 12 h. Data are presented as the fold change in Renilla luciferase-normalized firefly luciferase activities to corresponding DMSO control (set as 1). The differences in induced p3A4-luc reporter construct activities between HepG2 cells transfected with pOATP1B1 and those transfected with empty pcDNA3 plasmid were analyzed by an unpaired *t*-test. * indicates $p < 0.05$ and ** indicates $p < 0.01$.

Gene reporter assay 12 h-treatment HepG2 cells

Fig. 7. The effect of MDR1 overexpression on induction of CYP3A4 gene reporter by rifampicin and its derivatives. HepG2 cells were transfected with p3A4-luc reporter construct, pSG5-hPXR, and pRL-TK along with pMDR1 or pcDNA3 for 48 h and then treated with rifampicin and its derivatives at indicated concentrations for 12 h. Data are presented as the fold change in Renilla luciferase-normalized firefly luciferase activities to corresponding DMSO control (set as 1). The differences in induced p3A4-luc reporter construct activities between HepG2 cells transfected with pMDR1 and those transfected with empty pcDNA3 plasmid were analyzed by an unpaired *t*-test. * indicates $p < 0.05$, ** indicates $p < 0.01$, and *** indicates $p < 0.001$.

for 25-desacetyl rifampicin at 80 μM.

3.9. A rationale behind autoinduction of rifampicin elimination

In one week of repeated administration, rifampicin induces its own elimination leading to a reduction of its half-life. This is perhaps due to enhanced hepatic deacetylation and biliary excretion [4,17]. To describe expression changes in genes involved in rifampicin elimination, we challenged 2D and 3D PHHs with rifampicin within the time range of 4–168 h. In 3D PHHs, AADAC expression showed a non-significant decline in mRNA expression following rifampicin treatment as an early response, but inhibition was only temporal and AADAC expression gradually returned to its original level within 24–120 h (Fig. 8A). Next, rifampicin induced biphasic inhibition in OATP1B1 mRNA expression through tested time (Fig. 8B). Further, OATP1B3 mRNA levels were significantly downregulated by rifampicin starting shortly after its treatment (Fig. 8C). Finally, MDR1 mRNA expression was induced in a time-dependent manner (Fig. 8D). Results gained from 2D PHHs reflected those of 3D PHHs.

4. Discussion

Firstly, we noticed an instability of rifampicin in an aqueous PHH medium (Fig. 1A), which is in line with previous findings [10]. This could not be exclusively explained by its terminal autooxidation to rifampicin quinone, but a more complex degradation route is expected [32]. Recent work pointed out that rifampicin quinone in aqueous solution can be reduced in a temperature-dependent manner and thus reconverted to rifampicin even in the absence of a reducing agent [33]. In our hand, rifampicin concentration maintained at a very stable and low level in rifampicin quinone solution (Fig. 1B), nonenzymatic reduction of rifampicin quinone to rifampicin thus appears to be low if any under our conditions.

It is important to stress, that once rifampicin is used in experimental studies, one has to consider the labile nature of rifampicin resulting in the unintended presence of rifampicin degradation products with distinctive biochemical properties, a fact potentially leading to misleading biological conclusions. For instance, rifampicin quinone and rifampicin may differ in their pharmacological effects, as the former is supposed to exhibit immunosuppressive properties but not rifampicin itself [34]. Analogously, more efficient anti-Parkinson activities of

Fig. 8. AADAC, OATP1B1, OATP1B3, and MDR1 mRNA expression changes in 3D/2D PHHs following treatment with rifampicin. 3D PHH spheroids (donors 1–3) were treated with rifampicin (10 μ M) for an indicated time ranging from 4 to 168 h. In the case of 2D PHHs, donors 1 and 2 were only treated with rifampicin (10 μ M) for 48 h and 24 h, respectively. AADAC (A), OATP1B1 (B), OATP1B3 (C), and MDR1 (D) mRNA expression levels were analyzed by RT-qPCR. The data are shown as the fold change expression relative to the corresponding DMSO control at the same time (set as 1). ANOVA with Dunnett's post hoc test was used to compare time-dependent rifampicin-induced changes in mRNA expression relative to time 0 (set as 1) in 3D PHHs. * indicates $p < 0.05$, ** indicates $p < 0.01$, and *** indicates $p < 0.001$.

rifampicin quinone were discussed in two reports [35,36]. Similarly, both compounds have different antibacterial activity [33]. Finally, a lower-than-intended concentration of rifampicin may confound PXR-focused experiments.

Another issue to be considered is the *in vivo* relevancy of tested compounds with respect to their achieved concentrations in the body. Rifampicin reached a concentration of 10.7 mg/l (which corresponds to 13 μ M) in serum when analyzed 8 h after its oral treatment (600 mg). In the same trial, the serum level of 25-desacetyl metabolite was 1.8 mg/l (which corresponds to 2.3 μ M) [37]. But its times greater concentration could be detected in bile [38]. Comparable findings were also observed by others [39,40]. Consistently, rifampicin infusion of 600 mg lasting 3 h resulted in a peak serum concentration of 13.53 mg/l [41]. Interestingly, from post-mortem toxicological analysis of a case of fatal poisoning with rifampicin (ingestion of about 14–15 g), rifampicin liver/blood concentration ratio was assessed to be 6.8, which is indicative of rifampicin good penetration to the liver. Of the total amount of rifampicin found in liver tissue, 41 % was present as a parent drug, 28 % as 3-formylrifamycin SV, and 31 % as 25-desacetyl rifampicin [42]. Additionally, a high-dose rifampicin regime to the current standard dose (600 mg) is a subject of debate, as it could shorten the duration of therapy [43]. On this basis, it seems to deem micromolar levels of rifampicin and its derivatives achievable *in vivo* and justified for use in *in vitro* experiments.

Our data from gene reporter assays (Fig. 2) provide a comparison of rifampicin derivatives in terms of PXR affinity. Of note, both rifampicin

and rifampicin quinone revealed a similar potency to transactivate CYP3A4 promoter. The potency of 3-formylrifamycin SV and rifampicin N-oxide was relatively comparable with the other tested molecules. The only exception was 25-desacetyl rifampicin, which has a far lower affinity to PXR compared to rifampicin, which is in good agreement with the previous report [5]. While preparing this publication, 3-formylrifamycin SV was reported to greater induce PXR-responsive luciferase reporter over rifampicin [23]. To the best of our knowledge, other rifampicin derivatives have not been studied so far. Moreover, all tested compounds appear to be direct ligands of PXR as demonstrated by a two-hybrid assay (Fig. 2B).

Rifampicin is routinely used as a model human PXR activator. Importantly, species differences in a ligand-binding domain of PXR have been originally described. As a result, human but not rodent PXR is effectively activated by rifampicin. Likewise, PCN is a significant activator of rodent but not human PXR [28]. These findings could be recapitulated in our gene reporter assays employing expression vectors for PXR orthologs (Fig. 2C). However, up to now, it has not been known whether rifampicin metabolites and impurities could affect the transactivation of PXR orthologs. Present data demonstrate that tested rifampicin derivatives can impact the activity of monkey PXR but not rodent PXR. By contrast, 25-desacetyl rifampicin seems to have no or very low affinity towards monkey PXR as is also true for human PXR var.2. Another interesting aspect is that monkey PXR seems to be less sensitive to activation by rifampicin than human PXR. Lower sensitivity of monkey PXR to agonists should be considered once interpreting

preclinical studies.

To understand how rifampicin and its 25-desacetyl metabolite interact with PXR, *in silico* prediction was conducted using two different PXR structures [23,24]. The results document that tested compounds have varying PXR binding affinities. Unexpectedly, 25-desacetyl-rifampicin, a close analog of rifampicin, revealed a different orientation in PXR binding than the parent compound (Fig. 4), a potential unfavorable clash with H2 and no hydrogen bond interactions. Overall, this indicates that the acetyl group of rifampicin is essential for its optimal binding to the PXR receptor. The key residue for this interaction is Q285, which is included in the most important hot spot region of the PXR binding site [44].

As rifampicin derivatives could upregulate PXR-mediated CYP3A4 transactivation in gene reporter studies, we further tested whether the compounds could have an impact on CYP3A4 expression in a physiologically faithful *in vitro* liver model. To this end, we used 3D spheroids of PHHs generated on ULA plates, which have been recently shown to reflect a relevant hepatic functionality in the course of several weeks [18,19]. Surprisingly, 25-desacetyl-rifampicin significantly induced CYP3A4 mRNA in 3D PHHs leading to a time-dependent bell-shaped expression profile with the maximal induction on day 2 (being 2.6-fold). As previously reported by us [19], rifampicin provided a similar expression profile, but maximal induction was reached later not until day 3. It is worth of notice, that CYP3A4 mRNA induction is less pronounced by 25-desacetyl-rifampicin (1.8-fold vs 3.1-fold of rifampicin) in a corresponding time point of 72 h but still significant (Fig. 5A and B). This led us to the hypothesis that although 25-desacetyl-rifampicin has a much lower affinity towards PXR in gene reporter assays (Fig. 2), it could hypothetically contribute to CYP3A4 induction *in vivo*. This could be also the case for other PXR-controlled genes such as CYP2B6 and CYP2C9 (Fig. 5A).

Interestingly, rifampicin induced CYP3A4 mRNA more than three-fold after 72 h in 3D PHHs, which is a lower relative change than that previously observed in 2D PHHs. One has to consider that 3D PHHs express a much higher basal level of CYP3A4 mRNA, thus even low induced fold-change in 3D PHHs could mean dramatic changes in the total number of CYP3A4 copies [45].

In our metabolic profiling study with rifampicin, we proved a superior performance of 2D over 3D PHHs as the former could produce a main metabolite 25-desacetyl-rifampicin from a parent drug but not the latter. Importantly, previous experiments with human liver slices and microsomes could reproduce the rifampicin deacetylation process [46]. Our data support very recent findings, that even though a single 3D PHH spheroid culture has stable and physiologically relevant functionality, the insufficient low cell-to-media ratio may prevent to accurately predict drug metabolism. The authors suggested a multi-well spheroid system with its high cell concentration as a potential solution for drug depletion studies [47].

It appears that although the concentration of rifampicin quinone in cell-free PHH medium increases by a spontaneous autoxidation of rifampicin (Fig. 1A), a reduction is favored to a significant extent in 2D PHHs as no concentration of rifampicin quinone could be detected in PHH medium following 48 h-treatment with rifampicin (Table 1). In line, 3D PHHs seem to also promote a formation of rifampicin from rifampicin quinone (Table 1). Thus, the conversion of rifampicin quinone could be driven enzymatically rather than by nonenzymatic reduction as discussed above (Fig. 1B). This is supported by previous observations, in which rat liver microsomal NADPH-cytochrome c reductase could catalyze a reduction of rifampicin quinone [10]. Later on, NAD(P)H:quinone oxidoreductase 1 (NQO1) was another enzyme supposed to reduce rifampicin quinone [11]. Consistently, we could not see any significant rifampicin quinone-induced changes in ATP content of 3D PHHs (Fig. 5C). A spontaneous turnover of rifampicin to rifampicin quinone without its subsequent reduction in PHH medium could potentially lead to cell toxicity. The concern arises from the fact, that rifampicin quinone is a reactive molecule prone to irreversibly bind to

proteins and nucleic acids [10]. Instead, we detected a statistically significant reduction in cell viability caused only by 3-formylrifampicin SV (Fig. 5C).

Besides, the changes in the pH of the medium may also affect the stability of rifampicin. As shown previously, the amount of 3-formylrifampicin SV gradually increased in an aqueous solution of rifampicin at low pH [48,49]. In our unpublished experiments with rifampicin-treated HepG2 cells for 48 h, we detected a significant amount of 3-formylrifampicin SV in medium (Opti-MEM medium containing 5 % fetal bovine serum) enriched with HepG2 cells harvested by scraping. However, we cannot exclude another mechanism through which rifampicin is converted into 3-formylrifampicin SV in the setting.

Rifampicin has been documented as a substrate of OATP1B1 transporter, which is thus responsible for rifampicin hepatocyte uptake [12–14]. It may be thought that rifampicin derivatives also enter hepatocytes by OATP1B1 as suggested by gene reporter assay (Fig. 6). The assay associates carrier-specific transport of PXR ligands with CYP3A4 expression but bears some limits. First, other transporters may interfere with hepatocyte uptake of rifampicin and its derivatives, namely OATP1B3 [12–14]. The relation between PXR action and a total intracellular concentration of compounds remains largely obscure. Thus, intracellular concentration of rifampicin or its derivatives may reach a sufficient level for PXR saturation perhaps by passive diffusion and results in a peak PXR activity irrespective of specific transport by OATP1B1. This concern is illustrated by rifampicin treatment at 10 μ M (Fig. 6). In this case, we could not distinguish between OATP1B1 and empty vector settings, but we could do so in a lower rifampicin concentration of 1 μ M, where other transport routes may be less pronounced. As a precaution, we tested rifampicin and its derivatives in several low concentrations for a short period of 12 h to avoid an excessive intracellular influx and cell accumulation of rifampicin derivatives hampering to detect specific OATP1B1 transport. Analogically, we indirectly demonstrated, that all tested rifampicin derivatives are transported by MDR1 (Fig. 7), the data being complementary to the previous report, in which MDR1-driven efflux of rifampicin was unveiled [15]. However, it seems that high extracellular concentrations may override the efflux transport as no differences between MDR1 and empty plasmid transfected cells were observed at 10 μ M concentration of rifampicin or rifampicin quinone.

Rifampicin induces its own elimination during a repeated dosage resulting in a decline of its elimination half-life [17,50]. This auto-induction is believed to be mediated through enhanced hepatic deacetylation [4] with the 25-desacetylated derivative being the main rifampicin metabolite in man [46]. As AADAC was the enzyme identified to catalyze the 25-deacetylation of rifampicin [5], it is tempting to propose that rifampicin could upregulate AADAC expression and subsequently its own metabolism. However, in the previous study with 2D PHHs ($n = 6$), authors could not see any increase in AADAC transcript level, whereas only short-time exposure to rifampicin (10 μ M, 24 h) was interrogated [51]. Next, induction of rifampicin transport rate mediated by OATP1B1, OATP1B3, and MDR1 could also stand behind observed autoinduction of rifampicin elimination. This is based on the assumption that the cooperative action of uptake and efflux transporters could accelerate the biliary excretion of rifampicin and its metabolites. This agrees with clinical findings where cumulative recoveries of rifampicin and 25-desacetyl-rifampicin in bile increased from day 1 to day 7 of rifampicin continuous treatment [6]. Moreover, rifampicin has been also proposed to induce its presystemic elimination in a gut wall following prolonged rifampicin exposure [50,52,53].

With all those reports in mind, we investigated the effect of rifampicin on AADAC, OATP1B1, OATP1B3, and MDR1 mRNA expression in long-term experiments employing 3D PHHs (Fig. 8A–D). The basal expression of all tested genes was stable over a cultivation period (data not presented). Here, we revealed that uptake transporters OATP1B1 and OATP1B3 are decreased within long-term experiments in 3D PHHs. Similarly, the time-dependent expression profile of AADAC mRNA

showed a trend of a slight decline at the start of rifampicin exposure but maintained at basal level in the late phase being contradictory with the expectation. Moreover, we have recently demonstrated that rifampicin exposure is accompanied by upregulation of MDR1 in 3D PHHs in a time course of several days [19], which was confirmed again in this manuscript (Fig. 8D). As stated elsewhere, rifampicin-induced MDR1 expression was also detected in enterocytes of duodenal biopsies [54]. Patients pretreated with MDR1 inhibitor verapamil showed higher serum levels of ingested rifampicin [55]. These findings collectively give rise to a hypothesis that upregulation of MDR1 can accelerate rifampicin hepatic elimination as well as decrease rifampicin absorption. Moreover, 25-desacetyl-rifampicin may be increasingly excreted to bile as being a substrate of MDR1 (Fig. 7). Although other determinants in rifampicin autoinduction cannot be totally excluded, those are unlikely AADAC and uptake transporters OATP1B1 and OATP1B3. Of note, numerous genetic variants for MDR1, OATP1B1, PXR, and AADAC have been reported in the literature. However, there is currently no consensus agreement on the influence of intrasubject genetic polymorphism on rifampicin pharmacokinetics as thoroughly reviewed elsewhere [56].

Taken together, the current work for the first time described and compared the stability of rifampicin in 2D and 3D PHHs. In addition, it characterized rifampicin and its derivatives regarding their affinity towards PXR and their CYP3A4 induction potency in hepatocyte models including 3D PHHs. Furthermore, it shed light on a mechanism standing behind the autoinduction of rifampicin elimination as well as the disposition of rifampicin and its metabolites in hepatocytes due to their uptake and efflux.

5. Ethics approval statement

Primary human hepatocytes were acquired commercially as a result no ethical approval was demanded.

Author contribution statement

LS, TS, LL, RKu, and PP designed the research. LS, TS, LL, and RKa performed the research. LS, TS, LL, and RKa wrote the manuscript sections according to his/her expertise. TS, LL, and RKa made the figures and tables. LS, TS, LL, RKa, RKu, and PP critically revised the manuscript and interpreted data. All authors contributed significantly to this study. All authors have read and approved the final article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tomas Smutny: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Lucie Smutna:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Lukas Lochman:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Rajamanikkam Kamaraj:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Radim Kucera:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Petr Pavek:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Tomas Smutny reports financial support was provided by Czech Science Foundation. Tomas Smutny reports financial support was provided by Ministry of Education Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic. Petr Pavek reports financial support was provided by Czech Science Foundation. Petr Pavek reports financial support was provided by Ministry of

Education Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

This study was supported by Primus (110/13/221301, Czech Republic) to TS, by GACR (22-05167S, Czech Republic) to PP and TS, by student SVV project (260 663, Czech Republic) to RKa, and by the project New Technologies for Translational Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences /NETPHARM, project ID CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004607, is co-funded by the European Union, to TS and PP. The authors would like to express their gratitude to Zdenka Krajnikova and Michaela Hribkova for their support with experiments.

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